

The Exploration of Performance Evaluation on School Rear-service in China

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ABSTRACT

The logistic service in China's schools, especially in college schools, has become more and more socialized, which requires higher quality of the management to meet it. The performance evaluation about school logistic service in China includes six aspects: the effectiveness of the operation system, the quality of the school asset, the ability of the development, the service quality, the social contribution and the level of the management. This paper will introduce the current situation of logistic service management in China's schools, and then make an analysis of the school logistics performance management, followed by a design of performance evaluation index system of school logistics management, which includes 6 indexes and 42 sub-indexes, with the purpose of improving the quality of school logistics assets, ensuring sustainable development and perfecting the logistics management and economic efficiency. Finally, the paper will try to propose some suggestions on how to reform the school logistics service performance management in China and learn some useful experience from abroad.

Keywords: school, rear-service management, performance evaluation

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Исследование эффективности материально-технического обеспечения в высших учебных заведениях Китая

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РЕФЕРАТ

Материально-техническое обеспечение в высших учебных заведениях Китая, особенно в колледжах, становится все более и более социализированным, что требует более высоких стандартов его управления. Оценка эффективности материально-технического обеспечения в китайских вузах включает в себя шесть аспектов: эффективность операционной системы, качество активов, способность к развитию, качество обслуживания, социальный вклад и уровень управления. В статье проанализирована текущая ситуация с управлением материально-техническим обеспечением в вузах Китая и его эффективность. Затем, с целью повышения качества активов, обеспечения устойчивого развития, а также совершенствования управления логистикой и экономической эффективности, представлена система показателей эффективности управления материально-техническим обеспечением, которая включает в себя 6 индексов и 42 подиндекса. В заключение в статье предложен путь реформирования управления материально-техническим обеспечением в китайских вузах.

Ключевые слова: высшее учебное заведение, материально-техническое обеспечение, оценка эффективности

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1. The Progress and Management of Rear-service Reform in China's Schools

1.1. The progress of rear-service reform in China's schools

China's higher education has gradually changed from "elite education" during the 1970s and 1980s to "mass education" nowadays. With the expansion of the annual enrollment plan and the improvement of the living standards of teachers and students, and the increasing teaching and scientific research activities in the school, the traditional school self-run rear-service is not only limited in funds, but also inadaptable in management.

In 1985, the social-oriented reform of school rear-service was first put forward, which marked the reform in China has entered the initial stage. During this period, the school logistics department mainly adopted "department contracting" system or "fund contracting" system to implement the so-called "small organs, multiple entities and large services". Although this reform has reduced costs and improved economic benefits to a certain extent, the utilization of social resources is still low-efficient.

From 1992 to 1999, the workshop on "socialized reform of school rear-service in China" was held in Shanghai. At this conference, a paper *Opinion on Accelerating the Socialized Reform of School Rear-service* was issued, which marked the reform has entered the development stage. After preliminary exploration, many schools have generally recognized that the original logistics system "integrating management and service" must be gradually transformed into "a management department with clear responsibilities and a service unit (economic entity) with independent economic accounting and responsible for its own profits and losses". The reform model has also changed from the previous "small organs and multiple entities" to "small organs and large entity".

After 1999, the socialized reform of schools rear-service in China has entered the deepening stage. School rear-service was gradually incorporated into the socialist market economic system, and began to form a market-oriented rear-service system "dominated by government, implemented by social entities and selected by schools independently". The school rear-service presents new trend of specialization, collectivization on an enterprise basis.

Since China's school rear-service has been separated from the school administration system and began to move towards the goal of independent operation, independent accounting, self responsibility for profits and losses and self-development, the problem of management of school rear-service comes with it. The traditional management system of administrative institutions is obviously not suitable for the operation of modern rear-service system. However, the problem of how complete socialized service can adapt to the increasingly huge school assets has become more and more sharp, which has restrained the further development of school rear-service.

1.2. Current situation of school rear-service management in China

It should be noted that after decades of investment and development, China's school logistics departments have formed a large amount of accumulation and rich assets, occupying a large number of material and market resources. If they cannot be effectively utilized and managed, these assets will not only be wasted or even lost in the long run, but also affect the long-term development of school rear-service. In turn, it will reduce the satisfaction of teachers and students with it, which will affect the normal life and teaching activities in the school.

To some extent, the current school rear-service is still in a semi-enterprise state. The main service objects and markets of rear-service are still the schools, and most of the personnel still belong to the official establishment of the schools. In the long run, the service objects and work nature of the logistics organization will remain the same.

Schools will also provide the policy preference for these separated logistics departments whenever the policy allows and conditions are met.

However, with the reform of the school logistics system, the former industry access barriers have been broken, and some socialized rear-service enterprises have begun to enter the school campus on a large scale, and can provide more cheap and high-quality services and commodities (such as logistics, catering, etc.). In the increasingly competitive school service market, those rear-service departments which were accustomed to traditional administration are becoming less and less competitive in the market economy environment. At the same time, they are also facing many new problems. How to improve the utilization efficiency of school assets and level of rear-service? Most school rear-service lacks a set of systematic and effective management methods, resulting in the dilemma of unfavorable external supervision and chaotic internal management, insufficient utilization of resources and low enthusiasm of employees.

1.3. Problems faced by school rear-service in China

The school's rear-service performance goals are divorced from its functions, and branches inside the rear-service department also lack a clear self positioning. Generally speaking, the enterprise should pursue profit maximization, but the school rear-service department should not be simply a competitive one, and must adhere to the purpose of "service first". Therefore, the school rear-service department should pursue not only economic benefits, but also social benefits.

The school rear-service department has not yet become a real modern enterprise economic organization, or has not operated according to the requirements of the modern enterprise system. Research on the modern enterprise system of the school rear-service model and the application of modern management methods are also limited. The business scope of school rear-service is large and there are many types of service, which often leads to multiple leaders and difficult to define their responsibilities. Since the responsibilities are not clear, the rear-service departments do not have scientific post analysis and procedure design. The work task lacks standardized and regular procedure norms in operations.

School logistics administrators lack the objective conditions and subjective motivation to effectively implement internal control and management. First of all, the school rear-service, traditionally as a component of the school administration and serving the school teaching and research departments, is difficult to be an independent enterprise subject and give full play to its professional management advantages. Secondly, the rear-service department is lack of market risk awareness and cost pressure, lack of full authorization and effective incentive for managers, and a few key positions have huge responsibilities but lack of effective incentive measures. Third, some managers of rear-service lack professional management training, and their ability needs to be improved urgently, which affects the management level of some posts and the implementation of school decisions. The composition of school rear-service staff is relatively complex and there are many problems left over by history. Both in-service and casual laborers coexist. And the cohesion, stability of casual laborer is not so strong.

The assessment system of the school rear-service department is not perfect and lacks scientific management. For a long time, the performance management of school rear-service department has evaluated its economic behavior according to the mode of administrative management, which is not organically combined with the objectives of enterprise operation and socialized service of logistics. It can neither reflect the real performance of logistics, nor can it reflect the quantitative and operable evaluation indicators. The formalism of existing performance appraisal is more than its substantive significance.

According to the particularity of service objects and service environment, how to perform service functions according to market rules, and scientifically determine the

content, indicators and methods of school rear-service performance to reflect its characteristics has become the key point of school rear-service management.

2. Analysis of School Rear-service Performance Management in China

2.1. Clarify the objectives of school rear-service services

School rear-service should not only realize the service function, but also meet the requirements of economic benefits. The objects of rear-service are mainly teachers and students, and the scale is so small that it is inclined to form a “small but complete” self-sufficient rear-service, which makes the reform of rear-service socialization incapable. These characteristics show that the rear-service reform must start from the school’s own reality and forward according to the situation. School rear-service must introduce modern management methods and implement scientific and institutionalized management according to the requirements of the law of market economy. Those who ignore costs, do not engage in accounting and rely on administrative command management will be unsustainable. We should gradually establish and improve the cost accounting system and financial management system, and strengthen cost and budget management, so as to improve the economic benefits of rear-service. Logistics work should first serve the special consumer groups in the school. It should provide multi-level and high-level services, but not engage in high-grade and high-cost services like star hotels; it should not only maintain the nature of being diligent and thrifty, but also introduce modern and scientific technological means to truly realize the modernization of school logistics support and services.

2.2. Establish the operation system of school rear-service assets

We should implement market-oriented operation of rear-service in the school. The rear-service department should manage the assets on behalf of the school, realizes the paid use of assets, and establishes a clear internal settlement relationship between the school and logistics entities. The school rear-service department uniformly exercises the functions of rear-service asset operation and management on behalf of the school, and charges resource fees or rental fees for the use of the school’s real estate and other non-operating assets, so as to ensure the preservation and appreciation of the operating assets invested by the school into the logistics organization. It should follow the laws of education and market economy and change the rear-service operation mechanism relying on administrative allocation, and establish a market-driven operation mechanism and supervision system. The school should also integrate logistics resources, centralize management authority, and gradually clarify the relationship between rear-service and enterprises, transforming the relationship from “multiple A to multiple B” to “one A to multiple B”, in order to expand the service market, improve the value of resources and realize scale economy. The school should uniformly formulate the regulation objectives and policies of the logistics market, and maintain and improve the operation efficiency and service quality of the school rear-service market.

Strengthening cost accounting is an important content of school rear-service asset management. The specific measures include: establishing monitoring networks at all levels for all-round monitoring. For example, establishing centralized procurement management committee to implement collective leadership for material and equipment procurement, large-scale expansion and maintenance projects, and strengthen internal control and external supervision. Establishing and improving various rules and regulations to make sure there are rules to follow. To do a good job in management and monitoring, we must be pragmatic. We should focus on the key points and find the entry point of monitoring. In addition, various methods are adopted, such as questionnaire, supervision mailbox, report telephone and Student Symposium, to carry on the evaluation of service quality. For the assessment of business performance, index

analysis, report analysis and other methods can be adopted to achieve the purpose of monitoring.

The school's rear-service operation fund indicators need to be allocated down to various departments, changing from secret posting to explicit subsidy, from physical distribution to monetary distribution, and adopt the financial method of two lines of revenue and expenditure by clearing revenue and expenditure. The market relationship between schools and enterprises should be established to strengthen the management of logistics service contract and clarify the responsibility, rights and interest relationship between school legal person and enterprise legal person by contract. The business scope and items of logistics services should also be clarified and the service charging methods should be uniformly formulated.

2.3. Improve the development capacity of school logistics services

According to the characteristics of school logistics service, the economic components are diversified. Leasing and joint-stock system can be adopted, as well as the joint operation of school funds and enterprise funds, Chinese capital and foreign capital. Diversified management can make full use of the existing business resources, production potential and market advantages, organize a variety of commodities, provide diversified services, disperse the business risks of enterprises and obtain the maximum economic benefits. By developing a diversified economy and opening up new economic growth points for the school, we can not only rely on the school to engage in service work directly related to the school, such as commerce and printing, but also develop projects, expand operation, set up entities, face the society and the market, develop diversified operation, digest and absorb surplus personnel from teaching, research and teaching auxiliary departments to enrich the diversified management team. By opening the "canal" first and then release the "water" to drive, promote and ensure the teaching and research work with the development of diversified economy. Through the diversification of economic composition and operation, we can enhance the economic strength and competitiveness of the school.

By realizing the specialization and market-oriented operation and management, we can develop and expand the logistics service system, encourage the school's logistics service to develop industries, set up entities, adopt the methods of internal and external services. We can combine schools and enterprises to develop community economy, promote enterprise management, and enhance the ability of independent operation, self-development and self-restraint.

The school logistics organization should cultivate and expand itself according to the modern enterprise system and make it a market subject with independent legal personality. It should optimize the allocation of school and market logistics resources and realize the fundamental transformation of school logistics management mode and operation mechanism. We should follow the law of education and market economy, ensure the maintenance and appreciation of the operating state-owned assets invested by the school into logistics organizations, and take into account the interests among the school, the staff and the enterprises. It can be said that straightening out the relationship, standardizing management and supporting development are conducive to the rapid development of school logistics and improving the level of logistics management and service quality. Only in this way can the efficient logistics service survive in the fierce market competition.

2.4. Formulate school logistics service standards and improve service level

To formulate logistics service standards and establish service benchmarks is to make each service unit have rules to follow, models to learn and standards to measure. Realizing the standardization and institutionalization of logistics service is an important reform

content of the current school logistics work to “meet the market requirements and improve the service level”. It is a measure quality of school logistics service and reflects the overall management level of school logistics.

Normative services have two meanings: “what services to provide” and “how to provide services”. After the standard service is determined, on the one hand, the employees of the enterprise understand their own job responsibilities, organizational interfaces, service processes and methods, service requirements and facility configuration, and have clear objectives; On the other hand, the recipients also have a clear understanding of the services they enjoy. What’s more, enterprises have a yardstick when inspecting service quality and evaluating employees. The establishment of school logistics service norms should be formulated in combination with the overall service objectives and specifications of logistics organizations, carefully study and analyze various norms, fully consider the identity and operability of norms, and make our service behavior always focus on customers and ensure quality.

The realization of management innovation needs to be completed by people. Without people who understand business and management, no amount of capital investment can be effective, and no amount of advanced service facilities can be used. Logistics service is a dynamic process. To evaluate the quality of service, we should not only look at the result of service, but also pay attention to the process of service. The key to the quality of service process lies in the comprehensive quality of service personnel. The school logistics department is often regarded as an auxiliary department. Although the existing personnel are huge, there is an urgent need to introduce high-quality talents in logistics service and management. At present, the logistics departments of most schools do not pay enough attention to the cultural level, quality and skills of service personnel, which greatly affects the service quality of logistics services. The school should strengthen the training of existing personnel, carry out professional certification, establish a standardized technical level of logistics service personnel, and select and improve excellent logistics management personnel.

3. Design of Performance Evaluation Index of School Logistics Management in China

With the continuous market-oriented development of logistics service reform, the management mode of modern enterprises undoubtedly provides reference and thinking for the logistics management of Chinese schools. As one of the effective management methods, performance appraisal has been widely accepted and used. Performance appraisal has extended from enterprises to public organizations and government organs and from economic benefit evaluation to comprehensive management. Through the analysis of school logistics management activities in China, we realize that it is the great need to establish performance evaluation index system to meet the need of standardization of school logistics management, which helps to improve the quality of school logistics service and provide guarantee for the continuous deepening of school logistics service reform.

According to the requirements of school logistics service performance management and the research results of the existing school performance evaluation index system, drawing lessons from the enterprise standard performance management index system and following the scientific performance management theory, we have designed a school logistics performance management index system including six indexes and 42 sub indexes, which considers the problems faced by the school’s logistics service and the characteristics of management. While maintaining and increasing the value of assets, the purpose is to improve the quality of the school’s logistics assets, ensure sustainable development, improve the service level of logistics service enterprises and improve the

level of logistics management, so as to improve economic benefits, enhance the service ability of logistics enterprises and realize sustainable development.

3.1. Asset quality indicators

Indicators	Evaluation content
Depreciation rate of fixed assets	Average net value of fixed assets / average original value of fixed assets $\times 100\%$
Return on net assets	Net profit / average net assets $\times 100\%$
Return on total assets	(total profit + interest expense) / average total assets $\times 100\%$
Turnover rate of current assets	Net operating income / average total current assets $\times 100\%$
Total asset turnover	Net operating income / total average assets $\times 100\%$
Total debt / EBITDA (Times)	EBITDA refers to earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization

3.2. Sustainable development capacity indicators

Indicators	Evaluation content
Growth rate of total assets	Total asset growth of this year / total assets at the beginning of the year $\times 100\%$
Growth rate of operating revenue	Increase in operating revenue of this year / total operating revenue of last year $\times 100\%$
Capital accumulation rate	Increase in owner's equity this year / owner's equity at the beginning of the year (100%)
Degree of socialization	Ability to explore external markets: total external operating revenue / total operating revenue $\times 100\%$
	Independence: total school subsidies / costs $\times 100\%$
	Capital structure: total invested capital / paid in capital $\times 100\%$

3.3. Service standardization indicators

Indicators	Evaluation content
Operating activities	Proportion of main business in total business
	Product diversification (complete types, specifications, colors and styles to meet user needs)
	Rationalization degree of inventory quality (products, work in process, raw materials) structure
Service timeliness rate	Compare the average time from service request to service completion with the average level of the same industry
Customer complaint rate	Total customer complaints per unit time (e.g. one week) / total service provision per unit time $\times 100\%$
Customer service ability	Does the company have institutions or personnel such as customer advisory committee, market research and consumer satisfaction survey to understand customers' needs? Does product development come from market needs or customer needs?
	Does the company have formal procedures or systems to transform customer requirements into product and service design reform to ensure the lowest cost?
	Customer satisfaction with the company's products and services

3.4. Management level indicators

Indicators	Evaluation content
Management basis	Leader quality: credibility (whether there is any behavior of evading or rejecting debts), professional education, honor, development and innovation, and team stability
	Whether the production (business) management system is sound: quality management, material management, sales management and environmental management
	Whether the financial system is sound and whether the financial statements are credible
Management process	Does the company use Six Sigma or ISO9000 or QS or comprehensive budget management or annual business plan to manage and improve the company's work?
	Does the company use appropriate processes and systems to connect with other business units? Whether the violation of process system is supervised, managed and assessed?
	Has the company's management process reform improved the company's financial, human resources and sales situation?
Assessment and evaluation system	Does the company establish a system, process and standardized management for performance index evaluation
	Deviation analysis: does the company regularly analyze its business status and require the management personnel of each functional department to report on their work monthly? What is the quality of the analysis report?
Human resources evaluation	Basic qualities of employees: degree of specialization, training and stability
	Staff training intensity: $\text{staff training expenses of this year} / \text{total wages of this year} \times 100\%$ Employee training time: $\text{employee training time this year} / \text{total working time of employees this year} \times 100\%$
	Excellent talent reserve
	Employee satisfaction

4. Suggestions on the School Logistics Service Performance Management in China

The purpose of performance appraisal is to enhance the competitiveness of logistics enterprises, ensure the long-term development of logistics enterprises, and finally realize the best interests of teaching staff. In the process of implementation, we should start from the actual situation to select a breakthrough, from point to area, implement step by step and gradually put it in place. The school logistics department is a comprehensive department with many service branches, so the reform may not be promoted in a balanced way. Therefore, a breakthrough should be selected. Generally speaking, the breakthrough should be selected in the departments with mature conditions, prominent problems and easy to start. Through the full employment and competition posting of logistics workers, it can provide guarantee and good management atmosphere for the logistics reform of the school.

4.1. Optimize the school logistics management organization and straighten out the relationship

The existing management business of school logistics service is complex and entities are scattered. In the management reform, on the one hand, we should strengthen the asset management and operation function of school logistics service; On the other hand, under the framework of corporate operation, various forms such as foreign contracting, entrusted management and socialization are introduced. For example, external contracting, such as campus greening, flower house, barber shop, boiler room, can implement external entrusted management, that is, invite off campus professional companies or famous enterprises to manage the school entity. The socialization means to cancel or hand over those departments and entities that do not make profit and cannot manage themselves well to the social companies after accounting. In the operation of logistics reform, we should pay attention to the premise of serving the needs of teaching and research.

Actively improve the internal control environment of the organization. Based on the corporate governance structure, we should optimize the internal organizational structure, divide the management levels, clarify the responsibilities and rights of each responsibility center through appropriate authorization and entrustment, form a clear internal control chain, pay special attention to the improvement of personnel quality, strengthen the training of existing employees, and promote personnel knowledge renewal and structural adjustment. No matter how good the control system is, the incompetent employees will fail. We should make institutional arrangements for information communication channels within the organization to ensure the timeliness, integrity and authenticity of information, place organizational activities in real-time dynamic monitoring, and find problems, evaluate problems as well as control problems in time to minimize organizational risks. The information provided by the financial system is comprehensive, objective and measurable. Through financial control, it can be penetrated into all departments and businesses within the organization, and realize the whole process control over the controlled fields - including pre-warning and control, in-process behavior norms and feedback control, as well as post performance evaluation.

4.2. Improve the school logistics performance incentive system

In the reform of internal management system and operation mechanism, we can learn from the successful experience and practices of social enterprise reform. It includes promoting the reform of the joint-stock property right system in which the ownership and management rights of enterprises are separated, the reform of the personnel system based on the employment system, and the reform of the employee distribution system based on performance salary and post salary, etc. The key point of reform is to establish a personnel incentive mechanism and mobilize their enthusiasm. From the perspective of management, enterprises must establish a mechanism to stimulate enthusiasm and mobilize initiative in operation. The ways and means of incentive are generally divided into material incentive and spiritual incentive. At present, we should stress emphasis on establishing an incentive mechanism that combines material and spiritual incentives. The implementation of the incentive mechanism and the realization of the purpose of stimulating labor enthusiasm must be guaranteed through the evaluation means of "personnel" and "performance", and through the establishment and improvement of new standardized and reasonable rules and regulations. Therefore, the original systems must be revised and re-formulated. There are many difficulties in promoting the internal reform of logistics entities. The most important thing to solve the difficulties and problems is the ideological understanding of leaders and employees. Leaders at all levels should further clarify the objectives of reform, strengthen their confidence in reform, clarify their responsibilities, and realize that there is no other way to go. Only by actively exploring and promoting various reforms within logistics entities

can we promote the deepening, innovation and development of logistics socialization reform. The leaders must carry out publicity and education and positive ideological and political work for employees, and make full use of various resources and give full play to people's role through the reform of management system and operation mechanism. A new school logistics entity management and operation mechanism with unified responsibility, power and benefit, consistent contribution and reward, perfect management system, standardized operation and effective operation should be established.

4.3. Establish a service quality supervision and evaluation system

Revise and improve the original systems. Establishing an effective service quality supervision system is important to ensure the quality of logistics service. Service quality supervision mainly checks whether the services provided are achieved and whether the specified service standards are effectively met. On the one hand, it should inspect the performance of various service contracts and commitments; On the other hand, it need check the formulation, implementation and implementation of logistics organization systems and norms. At the same time, we should collect the feedback of customers' needs and expectations through the supervision system to timely improve the service system and norms. At present, the assessment system for employees is not perfect, and some systems and norms cannot be implemented and exist in vain. In view of these circumstances, supervision must be strengthened to ensure the quality of services.

First of all, the school should agree on the service with the logistics organization in the form of contract, including service specification, quality, remuneration, responsibilities and rights of service. Break the concept of "one family" and urge the logistics organization to establish and improve the quality assurance system. For the agreed services, we should strengthen supervision and assessment by means of random sampling, regular inspection, teachers and students evaluation and so on.

Secondly, logistics service enterprises should establish and improve the quality assurance system and strengthen independent quality control and evaluation to continuously improve their service quality and market competitiveness.

Third, establish an effective employee evaluation system. Whether the employees of the enterprise have achieved the services they promise and whether they have reached the service standards, their activity processes should be effectively controlled and properly evaluated. The evaluation shall be implemented through self inspection of service providers, patrol inspection of functional departments, special inspection and evaluation of quality supervision departments, teachers and students' evaluation, etc. Among them, the evaluation of teachers and students is a very important aspect, because it can reflect the results of employees' implementation of systems and norms and the effect of services. Comprehensive evaluation of employees' cultural cultivation, professional ethics, technical skills and service norms is a powerful measure to implement systems and norms and improve service quality.

4.4. Gradually improve the assessment content and constantly optimize the management work

The content of assessment should be focused, and each index is very important. The result is that there is no focus, so it is difficult to play the role of assessment and incentive. In practice, the performance evaluation indicators of school logistics management can be appropriately selected according to the characteristics of the school and the development stage of logistics services, and gradually improved in the process. If all indicators are evaluated at the beginning, it will be difficult to operate and realize.

According to the characteristics of the assessment object, the assessment indicators shall be selected in a targeted way, taking the service characteristics of different departments into account. In the design of assessment indicators, the assessment management

shall be carried out according to the requirements of the department and the characteristics of the post. In the assessment procedures and methods, the assessment cycle and result evaluation shall also be designed according to the characteristics of the department.

Logistics service evaluation should combine quantitative analysis and qualitative description, because there are many factors affecting teaching quality and logistics service. In the evaluation, we must unify the process evaluation and result evaluation, and pay attention to both horizontal comparison and vertical development. We should strive to make the evaluation results truly and objectively reflect work performance.

There are many methods of assessment and evaluation, but there is no general method suitable for all purposes. The basis for selecting assessment methods is to meet the characteristics of the school and achieve the development requirements and objectives of the school. We propose to adopt the assessment method of combining goal management with 360 degree performance feedback.

Determine management objectives. Rely on the upper and lower levels of the organization to identify their common goals, define each person's main scope of responsibility according to each manager's expectation of their own results, guide and promote the work with these value standards, and evaluate the contribution of each member. The goals must be clear, feasible, challenging, specific and verifiable, including daily and temporary responsibilities, goals to solve problems, creative goals and personal goals.

The evaluators of the logistics department include department leaders, colleagues, teaching staff (students) and themselves. Teaching staff are active participants. The completion of the final task and goal is evaluated by the superior supervisor, colleagues, subordinate employees, service objects (such as students) and self-evaluation, and the evaluation results are fed back to the evaluated. We must improve the authority and impartiality of the evaluation through the establishment of a cross management evaluation committee. Judging from the strong principle and policy nature in evaluation work, to ensure the scientific, standardized and efficient development of the evaluation work, a competent evaluation team must be established. Its members should correctly grasp the relevant policies, be familiar with the evaluation business, have a decent style, do things fairly, and have good sense of organization and principle.

4.5. Introduce and train excellent school logistics personnel

Break the identity boundary in the logistics department and implement the appointment system. According to the needs and the reality of logistics work, posts shall be set reasonably according to the situation and responsibilities shall be clarified. On this basis, limited term employment shall be implemented in accordance with the method of open conditions, equal competition and two-way selection. During the employment, the candidates should be selected according to its morality, ability, diligence, performance and future development potential. Those who meet the conditions shall be promoted to a higher level without being restricted by their original status. In this way, the best candidates can be selected according to the needs of the post, and the situation that once appointed and will remain unchanged for lifetime in the past can be avoided. This can not only strengthen the professional dedication of cadres and workers to forge ahead, study hard and strive for perfection, but also encourage young people to innovate with full enthusiasm and make the team full of vitality. Of course, to retain and introduce talents, we also need to strengthen the incentive function of distribution. Therefore, the salary income of employees must be directly linked to their post responsibilities and work performance. At the same time, we should gradually improve the wages of employees and implement special allowances for excellent talents, so as to attract and retain high-level talents.

Importing management talents from outside can help to introduce new thinking, new ideas and new measures, and improve the management level of logistics team. But at the same time, we should boldly promote those who have good ideological quality, strong professional ability and certain management level in the logistics team to management posts. These people are often the backbone of logistics services, and we must pay attention to protecting their enthusiasm. The introduction of talents focuses on adding new blood to logistics from management, technology and cultural knowledge, while the internal promotion of talents is to mobilize people's enthusiasm from the aspects of respecting labor, respecting knowledge, and realizing people's self-worth. Simply emphasizing the introduction of talents from the outside and the practice of exclusion and self isolation may not be conducive to the development of school logistics organization.

The quality of logistics staff includes professional ethics, moral cultivation, cultural and theoretical knowledge, professional skills, interpersonal skills, service attitude, service level, etc. On the one hand, we should encourage employees to spontaneously participate in various studies and training, continuously improve their individual ability, and give economic support when necessary; On the other hand, we should often send them out for advanced study or invite teachers to give lectures, and carry out systematic training in different majors for employees at different levels and types of work, such as inculcating enterprise ideas, learning management systems, standardizing various behaviors, etc. In learning and training, we should put an end to formality. The enterprise shall give preferential policies in terms of salary and treatment to the employees who have learned well and obtained the qualification certification of the industry sectors through study and training, so as to mobilize the employees' enthusiasm for learning.

The work of logistics workers is very hard, many of which are "dirty, bitter, tired and dangerous". In the knowledge-based environment of the school, the labor of logistics workers is not easy to be respected. Their status is at the lowest level, their labor remuneration is low, and their living treatment lags behind, which makes them be looked down upon, and they are more prone to a sense of inferiority. Therefore, in the socialization reform of school logistics, we should adhere to the concept of "people-centered" everywhere and all the time, respect the labor of employees, pay attention to the improvement of their working conditions and living environment, carefully study and deal with the reasonable requirements of employees, so that employees can make full use of their talents in their work, breathe with the enterprise with full confidence, share a common destiny and develop together.

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